

ROLE OF SHALYA TANTRA TOWARDS THE MANAGEMENT OF SPECIFIC DISEASES REQUIRING SURGICAL ATTENTION: A REVIEW

¹*Dr. Archana Kadam, ²Dr. Sunil Totad

¹*PG Scholer, Department of Shalyatantra, ²Guide Department of Shalyatantra, Rajiv Gandhi Education Societys Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital & PG Research Centre Ron, Karnataka.

Article Received on
25 August 2025,

Revised on 15 Sept. 2025,
Accepted on 05 October 2025

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17310597>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Archana Kadam

PG Scholer, Department of
Shalyatantra, Rajiv Gandhi
Education Societys
Ayurvedic Medical College,
Hospital & PG Research
Centre Ron, Karnataka.

ABSTRACT

Shalya tantra is an Ayurveda branch which is related with Ayurvedic surgery and provides many therapeutic regimens for the management of surgical conditions. The Ayurvedic surgery based on the principles and theories of Shalya tantra and helps to cure many pathological conditions. Vrana, Bhagna, Arsha, Bhagandara and Arbuda, etc are some pathological conditions that can be treated effectively using various approaches of Shalya tantra. Kshar sutra, Shastra and Anushastra, etc. mainly employed in the practice of Shalya tantra for the management of several surgical conditions. The modern approaches of Shalya tantra utilizes for appendectomy, gall bladder removal, hernia repair and chronic ano-rectal diseases, etc. Ayurveda Shalya Chikitsa facilitate debridement of unhealthy mass/pus/dead cells, the minor surgery offers advantage of early recovery so patient can join routine daily works just after post-operative procedure with fewer or no complications, Ayurveda Shalya Chikitsa reduces chances

of reoccurrence of infection. Present article explains role of Shalya Tantra towards the management of specific diseases which requiring surgical attention.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Shalya Chikitsa, Shalya Tantra, Ano-rectal, Surgery.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda encompasses great ancient knowledge about the surgery and surgical interventions and their utilization for therapeutic purposes. In this regard Ayurveda put emphasis on surgical interventions for the management of different pathological conditions. The Ayurveda created Shalya Tantra as specific branch for surgical purposes. Shalya Tantra presented surgical and para-surgical interventions for curing diseases and restoring optimum health status. This branch helps to cure disease like; cysts, haemorrhoids, abscesses, urinary retention, wound, urinary stones, ano-rectal problems and fractures, etc.^[1-4]

The Gudaroga Chikitsa used to cure ano-rectal disorders such as fissures, piles, abscesses and hemorrhoid, etc. The Vruna Chikitsa employed for the management of wound, chronic ulcers and cuts, etc. The fracture rehabilitation techniques used to relocate fractured bones and joints. This branch also helps to manage post operative complications and provides complete relief from minor or major surgical emergency.^[4-6]

Shalya Chikitsa requires some precautions while employing for the management of Gandamala, Arbuda, Ashmari, Stanarog and Mutravaodh, etc. The following precautions or suggestions advised while dealing with critical surgical conditions

- The selection of proper instruments prerequisite for surgical intervention.
- Maintenance of sterilization of equipments is required.
- Maintenance of aseptic conditions in surgical room for preventing chances of infections.
- The correct surgical procedures need to be adopted with minimal invasion and maximum benefits.
- The Marma points should be considered before surgical intervention to avoid complication.
- The dose and duration of anesthesia required especial attention mainly for critical conditions.
- The presence of previous diseases or history of illness should be taken in consideration during the surgery.
- Pediatric and elderly patient needs especial attention.

The Shalya tantra utilizes various equipments as mentioned below for surgical procedure

- Shastra as sharp instruments
- Yantras as blunt instruments

- Sutures for stitching purpose
- Bandages, surgical cloth other equipments, etc.

The pre-operative consideration of Shalya Chikitsa ensures complete preparation of surgery and makes comfort for patient as well as physician. The post-operative procedures prevent any chances of complication, provide complete health benefits of main surgical procedure and improve process of healing.^[5-7]

Shalya Chikitsa for Specific Diseases

Shalya Chikitsa used for many disease especially for ano-rectal problems such as; hemorrhoids, fistula-in-ano and pile, etc. Shalya Chikitsa helps to relieve symptoms of painful defecation, bleeding per rectum, discomfort in seating, constipation and burning sensation, etc.

Role in Arsha

Arsha is can be managed effectively with the help of Kshara Karma and Shastra Karma. The Shastra Karma and bandaging techniques helps in early healing of Arsha and reduces reoccurrence chances. Shalya Chikitsa when used with suturing technique in Arsha then it helps to control discharge, reduces burning sensation, cure itching and suppress pain. The post operative surgical intervention improves healing process and chemical cauterization of Kṣarasutra causes strangulation of blood vessel thus facilitate tissue granulation and fasten healing process.

Role in Fissure-in-ano

The Shalya Chikitsa facilitates relaxation of sphincter during the treatment of fissure-in-ano and boost up healing by enhancing regeneration process. Avagaha sweda of Triphala kwatha sometimes advocated as accompanying treatment modality in case of Fissure-in- ano along with surgical intervention. This approach helps to cure inflammation and reduces sensation of pain.

Kṣarasutra can also be suggested to relax sphincter muscles spasm; Kṣarasutra prevents discharge and improves natural healing process.

Role in Parikartika

Bhedana and Chhedana along with Ksharana can be used effectively for the management of Parikartika. The Shodhana, Ropana and Stambhana, etc. properties provides therapeutic benefits in Parikartika. The Ksharana action of ayurveda procedures helps to excises fibrotic tissue and facilitates removal of unhealthy debris due to their Shodhana action.

Role in Bhagna

The concept of immobilization and reduction play vital role in the management of Bhagna, however Ayurveda procedure of bandaging helps to relocate the position of fractured bone. Traction, opposition and stabilization followed by bandaging advocated for rehabilitation of Bhagna. Sushruta mentioned cross bandaging over the dislocation of shoulder joint.

Role in Vrana

The Shalya Chikitsa play vital role in the management of Vrana, the Dushta Vrana first converted into Shuddha Vrana with the helps surgical and purification measures along with uses of herbal medicines. Ayurveda mentioned Avasechana, Vimlapana, Patanakriya, Ropnam and Vaikritapaham, etc. as therapeutic approaches for the management of Vrana.

Mode of Action of Shalya Chikitsa

The surgical procedures help to maintain heamostatis and cure disease by entering into the deep routed tissue from where disease mainly arises. Incision, scrapping, excision, bandaging and suturing, etc. are major interventions of Ayurveda surgery which itself provides antiseptic action and prevent discharge thus offers health benefits in ano-rectal problems. The healing materials improve natural healing process thus restrict pathogenesis of wound and prevent further infections.

The cauterization of Kshara imparts Ksharana guna thus purify wounds and helps in tissue granulation.

The antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory materials like turmeric used in surgical interventions offers anti- bacterial action and restrict infection. The anti- inflammatory action helps to reduces pain and inflammation. Chemical cauterization of some technique helps to destruct pile mass. The chemical cauterization facilitates drainage of unhealthy tissue mass and fastens up regeneration and granulation processes to boost up recovery of affected part.

The Sutra used in Ayurveda surgery causes mechanical strangulation of vessels thereby facilitates removal of pile mass.^[7-10]

CONCLUSION

As per Ayurveda there are many pathological conditions which can be treated effectively with the help of Shalya Chikitsa. The Ayurveda Shalya Chikitsa play important role in the management of ano-rectal diseases (hemorrhoids, fistulas, abscesses and fissures, etc.). The surgical practice requires knowledge of disease, position of Marma points, and condition of patient and complication of surgery. The skilled surgeon should perform surgical intervention after the proper planning so to avoid any chances of adverse results. Shalya Chikitsa facilitates debridement of unhealthy parts, suppress disease progression. Support natural healing process with fewer or no chances of reoccurrence. Ayurveda advocated uses of Kshar sutra, Shastra and Anushastra, etc. in Shalya Chikitsa for the management of pathological conditions like Bhagna, Arsha, Vrana, Arbuda and Bhagandara, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Acharya JT. Sushruta Samhita, Reprint. Sutra Sthana, 33/4. In: Sushruta, editor. Varanasi: Chowkhambha Surabharati Prakashan, 1994; 120.
2. Acharya JT. Sushruta Samhita, Reprint. Shareera Sthana, 6/10. In: Sushruta, editor. Varanasi: Chowkhambha Surabharati Prakashan, 1994; 288.
3. Pandeya G. Charaka Samhita, Part-II, Chikitsa Sthana, 14. In: Agnivesa, editor. 5th ed. Varanasi: Chowkhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 1997; 342–76.
4. Das S. 4th ed. Calcutta: S. Das Publication. A Manual on Clinical Surgery, 1996; 55.
5. Sharma KR, Sharma SK, Deshpande PJ. Conservative management of Fissure in ano. Nagarjuna, 1973; XVI: 7.
6. Pandey G. Charaka Samhita, Part-II, Sidhi Sthana 6/61-62. In: Agnivesa, editor. 5th ed. Varanasi: Chowkhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 1997; 948.
7. Vagbhata, AstangaHrdaya, English Translation by Murthy K.R.S, 7th Ed. Varanasi, Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy, Sutra Sthana, 2010; 30/ 1-2:343.
8. Sharma S, Rasa Tarangini, Hindi commentary by Shastri Kashinatha, 11th Ed. Delhi, MotilalBanarasidas, 1989; 11/34: 583.
9. Dr. Anantram Sharma, SushrutaSamhita Part-2, Chokhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, 1st Edition, 2004; 159.

10. Kaviraja Ambika Datta Shastri. Hindi Commentary: Ayurveda Tatva sandipika on Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Sutra Sthana, Chapter 7, verse no.7, 14th edition, Varanasi; Chaukhambha Sanskrita Sansthana, 2003; 24.